

The Influence of Authoritarian Parenting on Children's Personality

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Abstract: We really need to know that authoritarian parenting is a picture of parenting that disappoints parents so that children become obedient. authoritarian caregivers greatly influence children's social behavior, as the results of research conducted by Meike et al. that authoritarian parenting style has a bad effect, which means that the higher the authoritarian caregiver pattern set by parents for children, the lower the child's social behavior. This article was written using a literature study method that which sources come from various articles that match the title and what problems are discussed. The purpose of authoritarian parenting is to make them obedient by suppressing control by their parents. The guarantor uses authoritarian parenting, which is tough, inflexible, and will be taught to improve both in their environment, meaning that we can conclude that authoritarian parenting to the child's personality is very important for adapting children to the environment around them.

Keywords: parenting, children, personality

INTRODUCTION

A child's personality is very important in helping them adjust to a new environment. One of the determinants of a child's character is the parents, who have the main influence in determining their character. A child with a positive personality will also be very successful. This is because of how parents help children in fostering their character from an early age. (Samsudin, 2019)

Character building efforts depend on the parenting provided by parents, parenting is the way parents educate, guide, discipline and take care of children so that they arrive at development according to the traits and norms that take place in the eyes of the public. The application of the parenting style has an impact not only on the quantity of growth and development of the child but also on the character

and social environment of the child as an adult. Any parenting style set by parents will result when the child is in a non-family social environment, namely playmates. (Sudiantha, 2014)

Hurlock states that democratic, authoritarian and permissive parenting are the three main categories that can be used to classify parenting. Each of these parenting styles has its own benefits and disadvantages. A democratic and rational approach is taken in this democratic parenting style. Parents who adopt this parenting style care deeply about meeting their children's needs and take into consideration their children's actual wants and interests. Children in authoritarian parenting usually do not have the freedom to make decisions, especially for themselves, because all decisions are made by their parents and are within their control, and they must obey them without having the opportunity to refuse or voice their opinions. Parents who adopt this permissive parenting style also give their children complete freedom. The traits of the caregiver are negligence, not giving excessive direction and control, even giving the impression of inattention. The child has full control over the situation. Many things, including personality traits, can be learned by parents through parenting. (Sari et al., 2020)

In this article we will focus on how authoritarian parenting shapes a child's personality.

METHODS

The writing of this article is made with a literature study method where the sources come from various articles that are in accordance with the title and what problems are discussed. With the literature study method we can read as many sources as possible related to the problem so that we can get results from summarizing the various sources we have read.

DISCUSSION

Authoritarian parenting is a type of parenting that emphasizes parental supervision so that children are obedient and submissive. Parents have a coercive, constrained, harsh and rigid parenting style where caregivers will make different principles that must be obeyed by their children without the need to know the child's feelings (Taib et al., 2020).

The characteristics of authoritarian parenting according to Hurlock in (Taib et al., 2020) are that children are expected to pursue every attitude of their parents, children often experience actual discipline, but they are rarely given praise or rewards when they achieve something. What's more, young people's behavior is highly controlled, and communication with them is poor. According to Bahran Taib (202) The traits of this parenting are that it is cruelly raised, tends to reject, shows little affection and love to its children, and convinces them to maintain guidelines and will generally limit the wishes of children. In addition, the tyrant parenting style has high demands and low responsiveness. Authoritarian parenting tendencies make children need encouragement, become disorderly, will generally question, and get angry easily.(Taib et al., 2020)

Authoritarian parenting styles greatly affect young people's social behavior, as the results of research conducted (Makagingge et al., 2019) show that authoritarian parenting styles make a negative difference, and that means the higher the harsh parenting style applied by the child, the lower the child's

social behavior. This parenting style will make it difficult for young people to get along or not confident when they play because children are afraid of making mistakes.

Furthermore, Yusuf (2006) interpreted that the behavioral profile of young people will be influenced by authoritarian parental attitudes. Children who are raised in an authoritarian manner usually show unfriendly behavior, cowardly, become moody, do not feel happy, are easily influenced, and have no clear future direction. Ignorant repulsion treatment applies rules that are too rigid, pays little attention to the welfare of the child, controls the child will have an impact on the child to be a little aggressive. A child's personality is shaped by rigid rules and punishments, which make them impulsive (they always follow their hearts), unable to make decisions, and hostile and aggressive.(Hidayati, 2014)

Endang Hadiani, et al (2021) said that the social-emotional development of children with authoritarian parenting patterns will result in the development of children, namely that they will be afraid of new things or recognize new environments, their emotions are uncontrolled, hyperactive, and shy, more silent, anxious, and less creative. many children whose parenting style is authoritarian have an attitude of lack of confidence and tend not to be able to control their emotions so that they are harsh towards others. (Hadiani et al., 2021)

In Fitri Handayani et al. that there is a relationship between authoritarian parenting and learning outcomes. This suggests that children's performance suffers from experiencing harsher parenting styles. This is because children who get authoritarian parenting experience tension and absence of opportunities that damage their mental and reduced learning outcomes compared to other children who do not get abusive parenting.(Handayani et al., 2021)

In his study, Wahyudi (2015) interpreted that one of the important aspects and aspects that can uphold students' extraordinary attitudes is parenting. The pattern of parental figures also affects the logical new development of students, including the improvement of learning achievement(Wahyudi Dwi Arif, 2015)

Similarly, an investigation conducted by Karnangsyah entitled "The Relationship between Parenting and Student Learning Outcomes and Its Implications for Guidance and Counseling Services" the results of his research can be interpreted that this parenting style affects the achievement of learning outcomes in students. The attitude and consideration of guardians, both from fathers and mothers to their children in completing learning tasks, will affect the learning outcomes achieved. As the information shows, hard parenting is influenced by both internal and external factors. A student's hampered health or lack of profound health is an example of an internal factor. For example, feelings of exasperation due to overly harsh parenting. This can roll back or reduce energy and interest in achieving a goal. (Karnangsyah, 2017)

Like research conducted by Lailul Ilham, as for the factors influenced by direction from authoritarian parents, one of them is low scholastic ability. When a child is told to concentrate every night and criticized for learning while playing, the person will feel enormous tension. This parenting style limits a child's independence in doing things, including things that should be taken care of by the

child themselves. This makes young people hesitant to just decide. Children are sometimes difficult to deal with, and when they are at home, they lack independence and are awkward because they are constantly watched by their parents. (Ilham, 2022)

The effect of authoritarian parenting on children's careers as in Asrori (2008) that the high influence of harsh parenting makes children not free, and children cannot follow their calling decisions. Children's freedom will be hampered by caregivers who prohibit excessively or use "don't" without providing objective understanding. This is the result of research led by Shafila in her article entitled "The Relationship Between Authoritarian Parenting and Career Decision Making in Students of SMK Teuku Umar Semarang" which shows that the higher the style of harsh parenting, the lower the degree of work, and the lower the authoritarian parenting style, the more career-related decisions are made. (Firdaus & Kustanti, 2019)

The main reason why parents apply authoritarian parenting to their children is because they really want the best for their children even though cruel parenting is not entirely right. Parents argue that their children should grow up with the education they were brought up with and maintain that their children should be able to achieve their expectations. Similarly, the reasons for parents adopting a harsh parenting style are also influenced by the childhood or culture of their loved ones. Parents who were once taught harshness by both guardians, they now apply it to their children. They argue that their children should grow up to be disciplined individuals. (Adinda Putri Maharani, 2022)

Personality consists of factors, namely: a. Internal factors: 1. Biological instincts such as hunger, a large appetite also constantly causes greed. and these traits become permanent attitudes. 2. Psychic needs such as security, respect, acceptance, and recognition 3. The need for thought, for example, various information that shapes one's perspective such as legends, religion, etc. b. External factors: 1. family, 2. social, 3. education. Factors that shape character in education, namely, behavior, traits, reactions, actions, behavior (Arkani, 2017).

Strict parenting can be applied during childhood, as it is a period of development and improvement for the child. During this period there is a fundamental development and progress of youth covering physical, mechanical, mental, and social areas - close to the turn of household events. (Asri, 2018). Authoritarian parenting patterns for children know no age limit, because in certain circumstances parents also need to apply harsh parenting to their children, for example when children act inappropriate morals and rules. Assuming that the guardian is being "gentle" at that time, it can affect the way children behave who like to argue and dare to parents. This can happen because the child's upbringing is too free without control.

CONCLUSIONS

The goal of authoritarian parenting is to make them obedient by withholding control from their parents. Parents use a dictatorial parenting style, which is extreme, unyielding, and will be forced to serve. They impose various standards on their children without showing any interest in finding out about their feelings. When children misbehave against their parents' wishes, parents become angry and

furious. According to certain experts, a child's development and progress can be hampered by fixed parenting. There is some evidence to suggest that tyrannical parenting can affect children negatively, but there are also many statistics that show how authoritarian parenting can affect a child's moral growth favorably. A child becomes determined to be respectful, polite, and loyal to his parents if the rules set by the parents are mandatory, such as praying. This is another advantage of authoritarian parenting. Authoritarian parenting can also make a big difference if parents neglect their children, which makes them defiant, difficult to justify and rebellious to them. This is because children feel that their opportunities are limited, restricted, and will be rejected if they make mistakes, which makes children act according to their feelings.

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